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DEVELOPMENT OF EFFECTIVE FORMS OF THE ENTREPRENEURSHIP ON THE SILKWORM SEED SYSTEM

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РАЗВИТИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНЫХ ФОРМ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА В СИСТЕМЕ ГРЕНОПРОИЗВОДСТВА

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Abstract. The article describes the role and importance of sericulture in the national economy, as well as the stages of the development of greening production. The proposals and recommendations on the organization of an effective form of entrepreneurship in the delivery of green to subjects involved in breeding silkworms are given. A scheme showing the steps of operation. It is recommended to study the experience of foreign countries in reproduction and distribution of silkworm seeds, and then they can be used in our republic. Particular attention should be paid to work experience in India. The Republic of India is the second largest silkworm seed and cocoon cultivator, but it is the world's leading producer of raw silk. The Indian government is paying more attention to public-private partnerships for the production of silkworm seeds. That is, the production of silkworm seeds is based on the specific requirements of the state, so the government will make silkworm seeds at the expense of the lowest costs.

Аннотация. В статье описаны роль и значение шелководства в национальной экономике, а также приведены этапы развития гренопроизводства. Даны предложения и рекомендации по организации эффективной формы предпринимательства в доставке грен субъектам, занимающимся разведением шелковичных червей. Предлагается схема, отражающая этапы работы. Рекомендуются изучать опыт зарубежных стран в размножении и распределении семян шелкопряда, а затем их можно использовать в нашей республике. Особое внимание следует уделить опыту работы в Индии. Республика Индия - вторая по величине семена шелкопряда и выращивание коконов, но она является ведущим мировым производителем сырого шелка. Индийское правительство уделяет больше внимания государственно-частным партнерствам по производству семян шелкопряда. То есть, производство семян шелкопряда производится на основе конкретных требований государства, поэтому правительство будет делать семена шелкопряда на счет самых низких расходов.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, silkworm seeds, effectiveness, support, mulberry plantation.

Ключевые слова: предпринимательство, грена, эффективность, поддержка, плантации шелковицы.

The silkworm seed and cocoon production are one of the ancient historical roots of leading on agricultural sectors of Uzbekistan. The advantages of this sphere are that producers have been applied traditional techniques and the agricultural methods had been deeply acquired as well, our producers are the rich experiences and the appropriate climatic environment can be got us several time production during in the year. The development of the silkworm seed sector has influenced the growth of export potential and can be increased the currency money, including to can be influenced by the flow of the local and foreign investments. Also, these sector enterprises are created many new workplaces; as well the majority women can be worked in the silkworm seed factories, so this way is great importance in rising of employment which is one of the highest importances of solving employment problem in our republic.

It should be noted, that as in all sectors, the development of sericulture industry sectors is directly depended to the silkworm seed system. So, we have to more attention for silkworm seed enterprises for can be got the high efficiency of the sericulture industry.

Nowadays, the silkworm seed entrepreneurs which is one of the most important of agricultural is the rapidly developed, at the same time the silkworm seed factories are being re-equipment new modern manufactures, as well the need to require to pay more attention of the process for new production capacities through with attract to extensive foreign investment in this sector. One of the main reasons for this we can get the highest quality raw silk through the quality of silkworm seeds. This will be increased the competitiveness of the products produced by the silkworm seed and then increase the flow of foreign currency to the country due to export to foreign markets. It plays an important role in socio-economic development of the republic. We can be more attended to analysis, in the 2015 year in our country sericulture 454646 boxes of silkworm seed were made and 26.293 tons' raw silk were harvested which is the 57.8 raw silk were got a box of silkworm seed, in the 2017 year which was only 451670 boxes of silkworm seed were made and 12900,4 tons' raw silk had been harvested. So average yield of a box was only 28.6 kg during the period of under analysis years. It was possible to see a box of silkworm has a mean yield of average 29.2 kg in the republic. The most noticeable, more 55,3 per cent silkworm seeds (they were 250000 boxes seed) were imported from other countries in 2017, of course, it's required high currency spends. In this case, that the sector has to solve bigger organizational, economic, legal and technical solutions.

Based on these tasks, in the 2017 year on 29th March, the president of Uzbekistan has made a new decision the number of PQ-2856 which is "Established on measures of Uzbekipaksanot", this has become the most important stage on the development of the national sericulture. One of the main tasks this association, these are being the creation of new productive silkworm seeds and production of high-quality seeds, which has been supported this decision. Aswell after 2023, the demand of seeds of sericulture is being fully satisfied by the local factories of silkworm seed.

Aswell, in order to ensure the execution of this decision the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan has made a decision on 11th August 2017 the number of 616about "On the Program of the complex development of Sericulture industry in 2017-2021", it is also legally supporting of the development silkworm seed factories. Undoubtedly, these documents are going to

serve as an important basis on the structural transformation and of intensive of the sericulture industry.

In our opinions, what the development of silkworm seed factories can be divided into three big part of stages, at the initial stages involved in the 1991-1996 period, at that time all seed factories had been produced only of the big state farms, which was controlled by the government. The advantages of this stage are that all state farms have cultivated silkworm seeds over the government plans, as well as a type of silkworm seeds, were distributed from only a single centre. However, at that time the new product type of seeds had not created, including the proprietary environment also had not supported. As a result, particularly no any science work on the creation of varieties silkworm seeds was carried out in this sector, accordingly this sector has been significant development lower. The second phase was involved the 1996-2015 period, at that time the cultivation of silkworm seeds and the creation new types of seeds had been considered as on the economic facet was not stimulated, because of at that time the mainly had being re-formed of agricultural system due to a great deal of attention was paid to farms activities, so the government had been more supported to farms who were cultivating to state order. As a result, the silkworm seed system and the cultivation of cocoon had not perfected due to the sericulture had been not developed.

The third stage was the period from 2016 to still now. the establishment of the Association of "Uzbekipalsanoat" has made new factories and silkworm seed factories including to which is supporting to attract of many investors, what is made a rotation. Figure.

Based on the information can be presented on the 1 picture, as follows enterprises are being acted in the sericulture sector while from after independent in our country. On the first stage, the silkworm seed factories have been acted to the state enterprises and then the silkworm seeds were prepared over the plans, at this system had been more attended only the capacity of products but the creation of new productivity seeds was not stimulated. At the second stage, the silkworm seed factories were being transformed into-joint stock companies, which also on the sericulture system had been formed the private business. As well as the silkworm seed factories were joined to the associate of the cocoons organizations, which was marked by the government decision. In the third stage, all the seed factories were privatizing who were making silkworms and they had been reformed the limited liability companies. The silkworm seed factories are acted to how are formed of the limited liability companies, that the possibility of private capitals is growing in this sector, as well the expenditure of seed factories are decreasing and the profitability is increasing.

The period of today's globalization based on the market required, so the system of production is going to require to more effective. In our opinions, the further development of silkworm seeds system which is making seeds and distribution process will be facilitated through the public-private partnerships. At the same time, the most seed factories produce for only to specific areas and delivered them to the farms who are located in this area. This method is being much efficiency on the produce and delivery of silkworm seeds to consumers, but it also has some problems. Including to:

- In the region is having an only one silkworm seed factory, which is not supported the competitive environment;
- many subjects live in other regions who are cultivating seed cocoons, so it will be made feature problems deal with to contract them for majority silkworm seed factories;
- The effectiveness of seed factories is directly dependent on the quality of cocoons and food supplying;
- Nowadays, the silkworm is insufficiently qualified staffs for the protection from various diseases and the direct monitoring to the cultivation of silkworms;

- the working periods time is not continuously on the silkworm seed factories, so many seed factories are forced to get seasonal workers.

In our opinion, the desirable has to study the experience of foreign countries in the system multiplication and distribution of silkworm seeds and then can be used them in our republic.

Figure. The stages of development are on the silkworm seed system

The Republic of India is the second largest silkworm seeds and cultivation of cocoons, but it is the world's leading manufacturer of raw silk. The Indian government is being more attention the public-private partnerships on the production silkworm seeds. That is, the production of silkworm seeds are being to made on the basis of concrete requirements by the state, so the government will be made silkworm seeds on the account the lowest spending.

Actually, the public-private partnerships are being to understand to mean that the state carries out some activities are based on beneficial cooperation with the private sector in the provision on certain services or products. In this case, there is organized a strongly competitive environment between several private sector enterprises, as a result of the quality products and services market will arise.

In the Republic's silkworm seeds system are applying to the bases of the public-private partnerships; first of all, it will be easier to obtain regular information on the quality of seeds and productivity silk. Secondly, secondly, the silkworm seeds cannot be produced only for certain a region's, but also they will be made to bases on their potential. Thirdly, the innovation will be supported which are being come to the silkworm seeds sector. Also, through this way will be become too developed of the capacity of silkworm seeds and their products also that can be got access to information on the variable market conjuncture.

In fact, the cultivation of silkworm seeds and the efficiency of reproduction directly depend on the fertile mulberry plantation and the cultivation of high-quality silkworms as well as the processing industry of raw silks are. The enterprises, which are activities basis on public-private partnerships will be strived for high productivity by reducing cost and high productivity by providing quality superiority. That is, the large expenditure is being spent on the seed cocoons on the silkworm seeds system, the private sector will be tried to make seed cocoons at the lowest costs.

I conclude, the silkworm seed sector will be developed by encouraging the public-private partnerships, which will be supported it and on the basis, the competitive environment will be organized. Also, the public-private partnership will be supported the creation of high-efficiency silkworm seeds and the fertile mulberry plantation, including to the development of sericulture industry is directly dependent on this way.

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